

Quantum Space-time Relation for both Massive Particles and Photons from Relativity

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We have argued in (1) that a Lorentz transformation essentially pertains to interactions, i.e. to pc , E transformations. It is not really an extension of the Galilean transformation which focuses only on motion. The point seems to be that the Galilean transformation considers motion applied to a particle with rest mass, and so the perceived new velocity is really linked with the new momentum, which is an interaction variable. The Lorentz transformation, however, considers different pc , E values for frames which move relative to each other with speed $-v$. Thus, there are implications on space-time, but this follows fundamentally from a transformation for pc , E , i.e. interaction variables, we argue.

In a number of previous notes, we argued that $x=ct$ and $E=pc$ are closely connected, in fact, one may set: $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$ ((1)). The problem is that $x=ct$ and $E=pc$ do not apply to a particle with rest mass and so a somewhat convoluted argument is required to argue that ((1)) also applies to such a particle.

Here, we wish to give a general equation from special relativity which holds for both photons and particles with rest mass and demonstrates ((1)).

Lorentz Transformation and pc , E

The Galilean transformation is entirely focused on the idea of motion. In particular, a particle with a velocity v_1 in a frame moving with velocity $-v_2$ relative to the ground has:

Velocity relative to the ground = $v_1 + v_2$ (where v_1, v_2 are vectors) ((2))

We point out, however, that for a particle with rest mass, even in Newtonian mechanics one has momentum ($m_0 v$) which is proportional to impulse. Thus, there is a hint that actually what matters are pc , E transformations and interaction variables, we argue.

The Lorentz transformation may seem to be focused on (x, ct) , but we have argued in (1) that since it also applies to (pc, E) , it is really about the effect of v on p and E , i.e. changes to interaction variables. Given that two frames are distinguished by a relative velocity, there are also implications to spacetime x, t , but the key is that these follow from the analysis of changes to p and E . Thus, there is no issue with c having the same value in a rest frame and as seen by a moving frame. C (speed of light in a vacuum) has nothing to do with p or p' and impulse hits because $E=pc$ (for a photon).

As a result, if E and p appear in a special relativistic equation together with x and t , we suggest that x and t are part of the relation as consequences of E and p and that if one wishes to think of the entire equation as representing an effect on spacetime, then E and p take on spacetime properties. We make this suggestion as a motivation for the equation which follows in the next section.

Special Relativistic Equation Suggesting that $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$

In previous notes, we have argued that for a photon:

$$x=ct \quad \text{and} \quad E=pc \quad ((3))$$

are directly linked equations. This led us to suggest that:

$$\Delta t = \text{constant}/E \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x = \text{constant}/p \quad ((4))$$

This result means that $E=pc$ is essentially the wave-equation

$$C = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength} \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is consistent with photon interference, but we note that ((4)) is obtained specifically for a photon. In previous notes, we have tried to argue that it should also hold for a particle with rest mass because p is momentum and E , energy regardless, but here we would like to present one equation, which takes the place of ((3)), and applies to both a photon and particle with rest mass.

We begin with an equation for a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at $x=0$ at t (at rest).

Then:

$$x'/t' = v \rightarrow g(v) m_0 c c x'/t' = v m_0 g = p \quad \text{where} \quad g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((6))$$

$$((6)) \text{ becomes: } E x' - p (ct') c = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Even though ((7)) was derived for a particle with rest mass, it also holds for a photon. We now use the idea that this should be entirely a space-time equation in order for it to have a meaningful interpretation. We note that one may write:

$$X' / (c \Delta t) - t' c / \Delta x = 0 \quad ((8))$$

if ((4)) holds. The condition ((4)) now applies directly to both a photon and particle with rest mass.

We note that x' (measured by someone in the lab with his/her ruler and t' , with his/her clock) is compared with the intrinsic gradation scheme of ((4)) regardless of whether one has a photon or particle with rest mass. Interestingly, it is $c \Delta t$ which creates a gradation which applies to x' and Δx , to $c t'$. (One might have expected the wavelength \hbar/p to be compared with x' and \hbar/E with t') We try to interpret this feature.

Given a 4-vector (x', ct') for a particle with rest mass, m_0 ,

$x' = vt'$ and ct' is the distance traveled by a photon in t' ((9))

If one has momentum p' , then even though this applies to a particle with rest mass, momentum is momentum, i.e. an impulse does not distinguish a photon impulse from a particle one. Thus,

$ct' / (1/p')$ may be thought of strictly as a photon result ((10))

$X' / (1/E')$ for a photon yields the same result as ((10)), but for a particle with rest mass, setting $c=1$, one has:

$x' = v t'$ and $E' = p'/v$ ((11))

Thus, the v from x' cancels the $1/v$ from E' for a particle with rest mass.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a Lorentz transformation specifically applies to pc, E , i.e. interaction variables for two frames linked by a relative speed $-v$. P for a particle with rest mass, however, is proportional to $m_0 v$ giving the sense of motion being bestowed upon a rest particle through the moving frame. In other words, the Lorentz transformation may be derived for pc, E , but has implications on space-time (not the other way around). We thus suggest that if one has a special relativistic equation containing p, E, x, t , one may try to interpret it strictly in terms of spacetime, meaning that E and p become linked with spacetime concepts.

We have argued in previous notes that for a photon, $x=ct$ and $E=pc$ map into each other, leading to the notion of $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$. This result, however, only holds for a photon. We try to find an equation which holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass. We argue that: $E x' - p (ct') c = 0$ holds for both. We note that the 4-vector (x', ct') contains two lengths for a particle with rest mass. The first is $x'=vt'$ and the second ct' , (the distance a photon would travel in t'). We argue that if one considers p' as momentum (which could be applied to either a photon or particle with rest mass), $ct'/(1/p')$ applies to both. Now $x'=vt'$ and for a particle with rest mass, $E'=p'/v$ ($c=1$) so the v 's cancel in $E' x'$. Thus, $E' x'$ holds for both a particle with rest mass and a photon. As a result, there is a single equation $E x' - p (ct') c = 0$ which holds for both a particle with rest mass and photon and yield the quantum feature: $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speed in Lorentz Transformation Directly Linked to Increased Momentum Hence Impulse? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)